

Melisa Valiyeva Orkhan

Junior Researcher, Evrika High School

Mahir Safarov Alisafa

PhD, Assoc.prof., Departments of Prosthodontics, Azerbaijan Medical University

Fuad Mammadov Yusir

PhD, Assoc.prof., Department of Therapeutic Dentistry of Azerbaijan Medical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13969422>

PREVENTION OF DENTAL IMPLANTATION COMPLICATIONS IN PERSONS WITH METABOLIC DISORDERS

Summary

It is important to note that the negative impact of metabolic disorders in obesity, as a risk factor for the development of periodontal diseases, on the course of the osseointegration process can also be the result of inflammatory-destructive tissue damage in the area of the dental implant.

Clinical testing of the proposed scheme of complex basic therapy with the additional use of the preventive agent White Glo Probiotic was carried out among 15 patients with obesity and peri-implant mucositis (Group I), 15 patients with metabolic disorders and mild dental peri-implantitis (Group II) and in Group III, which included 20 similar somatic patients, but without pronounced pathological changes in the periodontal tissues and peri-implant zone.

The data presented in this article indicate that the drug "White Glo Probiotic" had a pronounced anti-inflammatory effect in somatic patients with peri-implant mucositis. Thus, regular use of the prophylactic probiotic agent made it possible to eliminate pain, hyperemia and bleeding of the gums in the peri-implant area in the examined patients in a short time, i.e. after 1 month. As shown by the presented tabular data, the values of the Qugley-Hein dental plaque index in patients of groups I and II with perimucositis and periimplantitis with concomitant metabolic disorders decreased to $0.54 \pm 0.023^$ and $0.83 \pm 0.029^*$, respectively.*

Rapid regression of inflammatory symptoms including intensive plaque deposition, edema, bleeding and hyperemia was revealed in patients with perimucositis who received "White Glo Probiotic".

The use of this product in patients with peri-implant mucositis and peri-implantitis resulted in a significant decrease in the hygienic index and gingival bleeding index.

Keywords: dental implantation, obesity, complications of dental implantation, treatment

Introduction. An important aspect of implant survival is the prevention of early and long-term complications, which significantly reduce the functioning time of the constructions. As for the causes of late complications, the most frequently cited are errors in selecting the number of implants, surgical technique, irrational functional overload of implants and surrounding bone tissue [1 - 4]. The result of dental implantation can be affected by intensive plaque deposition and bacterial contamination, as well as associated diseases of various organs and systems of the body [5, 6].

Metabolic disorders, which are an integral part of the development of overweight and obesity, are at the basis of some somatic diseases that cause poor dental implant outcomes [7, 8, 9]. Obesity appears as a significant pathogenetic risk factor for the onset and development of a variety of serious diseases, including dental diseases [10, 11, 12]. When analyzing the relationship between obesity and inflammation, it can be said that obese individuals are predisposed to an increase in the level of certain biomarkers that activate the local inflammatory process and significantly affect the course of chronic inflammatory diseases [13, 14].

The actuality of the problem is associated with the widespread prevalence of obesity and the continuing growth of these parameters at the global level, as well as with the simultaneous aggravation of this organismal pathology and diseases of organs and tissues of the oral cavity, which in recent years has received increased attention of scientists due to the increase in the intensity

of intact teeth loss, against the background of disturbance of bone mineral density of the alveolar bone [15, 16, 17]. Infectious-inflammatory diseases of soft and hard tissues surrounding the tooth are more often diagnosed in overweight or obese individuals compared to patients with normal body weight. [18, 19].

The negative effect of metabolic disorders in obesity can be the result of inflammatory-destructive tissue damage in the area of dental implants. It should be noted that there are controversial results of studies of pathophysiologic mechanisms of comorbidity, etiologic factors and forms of perimucositis and peri-implantitis in obese patients. Microbial factor, functional overload, and the influence of systemic pathology are indicated as the causes of peri-implantitis [20, 21, 22]. As for obese individuals, the changes found in the area of dental implants were associated with a more pronounced impairment of clinical and radiologic parameters compared to individuals with normal body weight [23, 24, 25].

The above-noted facts emphasize the relevance of the works that study and analyze the immediate and long-term results of dental implantation in patients with severe metabolic disorders.

The aim of the study was to increase the efficiency of dental implantation in obese patients.

Material and methods. Clinical examination and treatment of orthopedic patients was carried out during 2013-2018 on the basis of the Dental Clinic and according to the research program of the Department of Orthopedic Dentistry of Azerbaijan Medical University.

The inclusion criteria of patients in this study were: patients of both genders with overweight and obesity at the age of over 20 years with various dental defects; signed informed consent of patients to participate in the study. Exclusion criteria were: severe associated pathology, oncologic diseases, viral infection, tuberculosis, as well as patient's refusal to be examined. Clinical and anamnestic, instrumental, laboratory methods of investigation were used, as well as clinical and statistical methods to evaluate and interpret the obtained data.

Clinical examinations of 90 patients, of which 50 were with overweight and 40 with normal body weight, included an assessment of the patients' general medical and dental status. The 50 obese patients were divided into three groups: Group I 15 patients with obesity and peri-implant mucositis; 15 patients with metabolic disorders and mild dental peri-implantitis (Group II). In these groups there was approbation of the proposed scheme of complex basal therapy with the use of White Glo Probiotic and group III, which included 20 similar somatic patients without pronounced pathological changes in the periodontal tissues and peri-implant zone. Dental status was assessed on the basis of the dynamics of hygienic and periodontal indices; plaque index according to Quigley and Nein (1962) - to assess the amount of plaque and hygienic condition, periodontal index (Periodontal Index, PI, Russel, 1996) - to assess the degree of inflammation and destructive changes, index Muhlemann H.R., Cowell I., 1975 to determine the degree of gingival bleeding. The studies were performed before and 1 month after the beginning of treatment and prophylactic measures.

Statistical processing of data was carried out on a personal computer using the Statistica 7.0. application program package and Excell 2013 standard statistical analysis package. Descriptive statistics of quantitative features included estimation of arithmetic mean (M), standard error of mean ($\pm m$). Student's t-test was used to evaluate intergroup differences, and Fisher's exact test was used to select the most informative features. The Mann-Whitney U-test was used to assess differences between two independent samples in the level of any quantitative trait. The critical level of reliability of the null statistical hypothesis (the absence of significant differences or factor influences) was taken as $p \leq 0.05$.

Research results and their discussion. The study included patients with overweight and complications of dental implantation. At the same time, combined manifestations of background somatic pathology were most often observed in older age groups and in males. The minimum indicators on frequency of perimucositis and peri-implantitis in persons with excessive body weight

were fixed in the age group of 31-40 years. A similar situation was observed in the control group. The gender and age distribution of the individuals included in the study is presented in the table below. In the course of this scientific study, the clinical evaluation of the state of oral tissues in a comparative aspect before and after the start of therapeutic and preventive measures was assessed in the patients of the main group ($n=50$), suffering from metabolic disorders and obesity, divided into three subgroups and in two groups the basic pathology was associated with complications of dental implantation in the form of perimucositis and peri-implantitis, while the third group was represented by patients with excessive body weight but without pathological changes in peri-implant tissues. The following table presents statistical data characterizing the degree of changes in hygienic and periodontal indices and showing the level of pathological disorders of inflammatory and destructive genesis in peri-implant tissues before the beginning of the course of basic therapy.

According to the obtained results, the inflammatory process around the implant was more pronounced in the patients of the second group, characterized by excessive body weight and at the same time inflammation of soft tissues and initial destruction of bone tissue around the implant (Table 1). At the same time, the data on all studied clinical indices, against the background of metabolic disorders, significantly increased the indices registered in the third group ($p < 0.05$). Among the subjects with peri-implant mucositis hyperemia of interimplant and peri-implant gingiva was observed more often, also complaints of gingival painfulness and bleeding were revealed in parallel.

The state of periodontal tissues and peri-implant gingiva, which was determined by the Muhlemann gingival bleeding index and Russel periodontal index, proved the presence of a pronounced inflammatory process in both groups of patients with perimucositis and peri-implantitis. Thus, Muhlemann gingival bleeding index values were $2,16 \pm 0,047$ and $2,39 \pm 0,021$, respectively, in the first and second groups, clinically manifested by bleeding of medium or high degree. We did not observe this in the dental examination of the individuals included in the third group ($p < 0.05$). In connection with the assigned tasks, all patients were examined clinically to assess the state of oral hygiene according to the Qugley-Hein plaque index, according to which the amount of soft plaque and its prevalence were greater in group II of patients with obesity and peri-implantitis (2.04 ± 0.05 , against 1.31 ± 0.027 and 0.23 ± 0.019 values of the hygiene index found in groups I and III).

Table 1.

Oral cavity condition in patients with overweight and dental implantation complication before the treatment

Index, scores	Group of patients		
	I Group, n=15	II Group, n=15	III Group, n=20
Qugley-Hein	1,31±0,027*	2,04±0,051*	0,23±0,019
SBI	2,16±0,047*	2,39±0,021*	0
PI	0,83±0,018*	4,94±0,081*	0

Note: * - indicators significantly different from those in group III, at $p < 0.05$ (Mann-Whitney U-criterion)

Thus, when analyzing the characteristics of the state of periodontium and peri-implant tissues in the first two groups of patients, a tendency of deterioration after dental implantation of the average indices of the studied hygienic and periodontal indices was established.

The examined patients with the organism pathology and inflammatory-destructive complications of dental implantation underwent pathogenetically substantiated anti-inflammatory therapy of stomatological nature with application of adequate volume of measures of professional oral hygiene with prior training of patients with implants in the rules of individual hygiene and additional prescription of controlled brushing with probiotic toothpaste White Glo Probiotic.

In 1 month after the beginning of these therapeutic and prophylactic measures the periodontal (implantologic) status was studied and estimated again (Table 2). As the presented table data show, the values of the

plaque index Qugley-Hein in the patients of the I-st and II-st groups with perimucositis and peri-implantitis with associated metabolic disorders decreased to $0,54 \pm 0,023^*$ and $0,83 \pm 0,029^*$, respectively. In patients of the second observation group 1 month after the beginning of periodontal treatment and prophylactic measures at the assessment of tissues condition by means of Russel index there is a tendency to its increase that, in our opinion, is associated with certain difficulties after a one-month course of conservative treatment in achieving a pronounced reduction in the indices of the depth of gingival pockets and the degree of destruction of bone tissue around implants. Along with this, the index evaluation of the changes occurring in the gingival tissues after the treatment of perimucositis and peri-implantitis in patients with concomitant organismal pathology after the use of a special toothpaste showed a significant improvement of the hygienic state of the oral cavity and reduction of gingival bleeding.

Table 2.

Periodontal status in patients with obesity and complications of dental implantation, one month after the start of treatment and preventive measures

Index, scores	Group of patients		
	I Group, n=15	II Group, n=15	III Group, n=20
Qugley-Hein	0,54±0,023*	0,83±0,029*	0
SBI	0,39±0,021*	0,73±0,027*	0
PI	0,78±0,015*	5,09±0,074*	0

Note: * - indicators significantly different from those in group III, at $p < 0.05$ (Mann-Whitney U-criterion)

The results of the study indicate a significant positive role of complex basic therapy, including elements of additional supportive therapy, in the management of the category of patients included in the study. In this aspect, we obtained the most significant results after the start of therapy in obese patients with perimucositis. Whereas in patients with similar metabolic disorders in the body, but with comparatively more severe pathological changes in peri-implant tissues the least positive dynamics was observed, especially in periodontal PI index.

Treatment of inflammatory diseases of periodontal and peri-implant tissues includes professional oral hygiene with additional use of antiseptic, antimicrobial drugs. In recent decades, the attention of specialists has been focused on the anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and bacteriostatic properties of probiotic remedies and products of plant origin, providing to some extent the restoration of the local immune system, normal microflora and possessing antagonistic activity against opportunistic and pathogenic microorganisms [26, 27]. The data presented in this article indicate that the preparation "White Glo Probiotic" in somatic patients with peri-implant mucositis had a significant anti-inflammatory effect. Thus, regular use of the prophylactic probiotic agent allowed to achieve the elimination of pain, hyperemia and bleeding of gums in the peri-implant region in a short period of time, i.e. in 1 month.

After the beginning of the proposed treatment strategy, there was a reliable decrease in the values of indices, which are used as objective criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of treatment and characterize the state of oral hygiene and soft tissues surrounding implants. Thus, according to the results of our research and the opinion of many foreign authors [28, 29], the signs of inflammatory reaction in overweight patients suffering from complications of dental implantation, in particular, perimucositis, can be significantly minimized by the optimal choice of methods and means having both therapeutic and preventive effects, which will avoid the development of more severe and deep pathological changes in soft and hard peri-implant tissues.

Conclusions. Rapid regression of inflammatory symptoms including intensive plaque deposition, edema, bleeding and hyperemia was revealed in patients with perimucositis who received "White Glo Probiotic".

The use of this product in patients with peri-implant mucositis and peri-implantitis resulted in a significant decrease in the hygienic index and gingival bleeding index.

References

1. Chen CH, Pei X, Tulu US, Aghvami M, Chen CT, Gaudillière D, Arioka M, Maghazeh Moghim M, Bahat O, Kolinski M, Crosby TR, Felderhoff A, Brunski JB, Helms JA. A Comparative Assessment of Implant Site Viability in Humans and Rats. *J Dent Res.* 2018 Apr;97(4):451-459. doi: 10.1177/0022034517742631.

2. Gupta S, Gupta H, Tandan A. Technical complications of implant-causes and management: A comprehensive review. *Natl J Maxillofac Surg.* 2015 Jan-Jun;6(1):3-8. doi: 10.4103/0975-5950.168233.

3. Hanif A, Qureshi S, Sheikh Z, Rashid H. Complications in implant dentistry. *Eur J Dent.* 2017 Jan-Mar;11(1):135-140. doi: 10.4103/ejd.ejd_340_16.

4. Panahov N.A., Makhmudov V.S., Mammadov F.Y. Finite element method for the study of stresses in the implant and the surrounding bone in improving the quality of treatment of complete adentia *Actual Dentistry,* 2022; Issue 3-4; p.56-56. DOI: 10.33295/1992-576X-2022-3-56

5. Kligman S, Ren Z, Chung CH, Perillo MA, Chang YC, Koo H, Zheng Z, Li C. The Impact of Dental Implant Surface Modifications on Osseointegration and Biofilm Formation. *J Clin Med.* 2021 Apr 12;10(8):1641. doi: 10.3390/jcm10081641.

6. Rotim Ž, Pelivan I, Sabol I, Sušić M, Čatić A, Bošnjak AP. THE EFFECT OF LOCAL AND SYSTEMIC FACTORS ON DENTAL IMPLANT FAILURE - ANALYSIS OF 670 PATIENTS WITH 1260 IMPLANTS. *Acta Clin Croat.* 2022 Feb;60(3):367-372. doi: 10.20471/acc.2021.60.03.05.

7. Banach W, Nitschke K, Krajewska N, Mongiało W, Matuszak O, Muszyński J, Skrypnik D. The Association between Excess Body Mass and Disturbances in Somatic Mineral Levels. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2020 Oct 3;21(19):7306. doi: 10.3390/ijms21197306.

8. Martemucci G, Fracchiolla G, Muraglia M, Tardugno R, Dibenedetto RS, D'Alessandro AG. Metabolic Syndrome: A Narrative Review from the Oxidative Stress to the Management of Related Diseases. *Antioxidants.* 2023; 12(12):2091. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox12122091>

9. Yang M, Liu S, Zhang C. The Related Metabolic Diseases and Treatments of Obesity. *Healthcare.* 2022; 10(9):1616. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare10091616>

10. Berger NA. Obesity and cancer pathogenesis. *Ann N Y Acad Sci.* 2014 Apr;1311:57-76. doi: 10.1111/nyas.12416.

11. Issrani R, Reddy J, Bader AK, Albalawi RFH, Alserhani EDM, Alruwaili DSR, Alanazi GRA, Alruwaili NSR, Sghaireen MG, Rao K. Exploring an Association between Body Mass Index and Oral Health-A Scoping Review. *Diagnostics (Basel).* 2023 Feb 27;13(5):902. doi: 10.3390/diagnostics13050902.

12. WHO, (2021). Draft Recommendations for the Prevention and Management of Obesity over the Life Course, Including Potential Targets. World Health Organization, Geneva, Switzerland.

13. Cobos-Palacios L, Ruiz-Moreno MI, Vilches-Perez A, Vargas-Candela A, Muñoz-Úbeda M, Benítez Porres J, Navarro-Sanz A, Lopez-Carmona MD, Sanz-Canovas J, Perez-Belmonte LM, Mancebo-Sevilla JJ, Gomez-Huelgas R, Bernal-Lopez MR. Metabolically healthy obesity: Inflammatory biomarkers and adipokines in elderly population. *PLoS One.* 2022 Jun 9;17(6):e0265362. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0265362.

14. Kościuszko M, Buczyńska A, Łuka K, Duraj E, Żuk-Czerniawska K, Adamska A, Siewko K, Wiatr

- A, Krętowski AJ and Popławska-Kita A (2024) Assessing the impact of body composition, metabolic and oxidative stress parameters on insulin resistance as a prognostic marker for reactive hypoglycemia: a cross-sectional study in overweight, obese, and normal weight individuals. *Front. Pharmacol.* 15:1329802. doi: 10.3389/fphar.2024.1329802
15. Lin X and Li H (2021) Obesity: Epidemiology, Pathophysiology, and Therapeutics. *Front. Endocrinol.* 12:706978. doi: 10.3389/fendo.2021.706978
16. Piñar-Gutierrez A, García-Fontana C, García-Fontana B, Muñoz-Torres M. Obesity and Bone Health: A Complex Relationship. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2022 Jul 27;23(15):8303. doi: 10.3390/ijms23158303.
17. Zhao P, Xu A, Leung WK. Obesity, Bone Loss, and Periodontitis: The Interlink. *Biomolecules.* 2022 Jun 22;12(7):865. doi: 10.3390/biom12070865.
18. Khan MS, Alasqah M, Alammam LM, Alkhairbari Y. Obesity and periodontal disease: A review. *J Family Med Prim Care.* 2020 Jun 30;9(6):2650-2653. doi: 10.4103/jfmpc.jfmpc_283_20.
19. Martinez-Herrera M, Silvestre-Rangil J, Silvestre FJ. Association between obesity and periodontal disease. A systematic review of epidemiological studies and controlled clinical trials. *Med Oral Patol Oral Cir Bucal.* 2017 Nov 1;22(6):e708-e715. doi: 10.4317/medoral.21786.
20. Astolfi V, Ríos-Carrasco B, Gil-Mur FJ, Ríos-Santos JV, Bullón B, Herrero-Climent M, Bullón P. Incidence of Peri-Implantitis and Relationship with Different Conditions: A Retrospective Study. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2022 Mar 31;19(7):4147. doi: 10.3390/ijerph19074147.
21. Benedek C, Kerekes-Máthé B, Bereşescu L, Buka IZ, Bardocz-Veres Z, Geréb I, Mártha KI, Jánosi KM. Influencing Factors Regarding the Severity of Peri-Implantitis and Peri-Implant Mucositis. *Diagnostics.* 2024; 14(14):1573. <https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics14141573>
22. Ortiz-Echeverri AM, Gallego-González C, Castaño-Granada MC, Tobón-Arroyave SI. Risk indicators associated with peri-implant diseases: a retrospective cross-sectional study of Colombian patients with 1 to 18 years of follow-up. *J Periodontol Implant Sci.* 2024 Jun;54(3):161-176. doi: 10.5051/jpis.2300140007.
23. Alkudhairy F, Vohra F, Al-Kheraif AA, Akram Z. Comparison of clinical and radiographic peri-implant parameters among obese and non-obese patients: A 5-year study. *Clin Implant Dent Relat Res.* 2018 Oct;20(5):756-762. doi: 10.1111/cid.12633.
24. Arslan ZB. Evaluation of the Relationship Between Oral Health and Body Mass Index. *Eurasian J Med.* 2023 Oct;55(3):259-262. doi: 10.5152/eurasianjmed.2023.23272.
25. Sam L, Chattipakorn S, Khongkhunthian P. Obesity and dental implant treatment: a review. *J Osseointegr* 2018;10(3):95-102. DOI10.23805/JO.2018.10.03.05
26. Nuttall FQ. Body Mass Index: Obesity, BMI, and Health: A Critical Review. *Nutr Today.* 2015 May;50(3):117-128. doi: 10.1097/NT.0000000000000092.
27. WHO, (2020). Obesity and Overweight. World Health Organization, Geneva, Switzerland. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/obesity-and-overweigh>.
28. Aliyeva E, Hasanov A, Musayev J, Mammadov F. Effect of thyme extract on experimental periodontitis in rabbits: study with histologic control. *Oral Surgery, Oral Medicine, Oral Pathology and Oral Radiology.* 2015 Mar 1; 119 (3):e151. DOI:10.1016/j.oooo.2014.07.540
29. Allaker RP, Stephen AS. Use of Probiotics and Oral Health. *Curr Oral Health Rep.* 2017;4(4):309-318. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40496-017-0159-6>